

Fatal Mucocutaneous Manifestation of Acute Monocytic Leukemia: A Rare Case Report

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ABSTRACT

This case report describes a rare and clinically significant instance of mucocutaneous involvement in a 77-year-old male, ultimately diagnosed with acute monocytic leukemia. The patient presented with progressive erythematous papular lesions affecting the trunk, back, scalp, face, and neck, accompanied by dysphagia for solids. Initial clinical suspicion pointed to a primary cutaneous lymphoma. However, extensive mucosal involvement was identified via nasofibroscopy, with lesions affecting the nasopharynx, oropharynx, and laryngeal structures. Diagnostic workup, including histopathology and flow cytometry from skin and bone marrow biopsies, confirmed acute monocytic leukemia with cutaneous involvement (leukemia cutis). This case underscores the importance of considering hematologic malignancies in patients with atypical mucocutaneous presentations and highlights the necessity of a multidisciplinary approach for accurate diagnosis and management.

Keywords: Leukemia cutis; Mucocutaneous involvement; Acute monocytic leukemia; Erythematous papular lesions

This case report highlights a rare and clinically significant instance of mucocutaneous involvement in a 77-year-old male, ultimately diagnosed with acute monocytic leukemia. He initially presented at the emergency department with progressive erythematous papular lesions that had appeared two weeks prior, first on his trunk and back, then spreading to his scalp, face, and neck. He reported dysphagia for solids but denied any associated pain, itching, fever, respiratory, gastrointestinal, or neurological symptoms.

On examination, multiple papular lesions of varying sizes were observed, notably on his lower left eyelid, eyebrow, forehead, mid-face, chin, and lower neck (Figures 1a-b), as well as on his trunk and back. Primary diagnostic suspicion centered on a primary cutaneous lymphoma.

A consult with the ENT department led to nasofibroscopy, revealing severe mucosal involvement. Lesions were observed on the posterior and lateral walls of the nasopharynx, with some contacting the uvula (Figure 2a), and further down in the oropharynx, where submucosal masses were noted, displacing the epiglottis (Figure 2b).

Both pyriform sinuses, the laryngeal epiglottic surface, aryepiglottic folds, ventricular folds, and anterior subglottic space were affected, though vocal fold mobility was preserved (Figure 3a-b).

Blood tests and biopsies from a trunk lesion and iliac crest bone marrow were taken for histopathology and flow cytometry. These confirmed a diagnosis of acute monocytic leukemia with cutaneous involvement (leukemia cutis).

The patient received multiple chemotherapeutic regimens and corticosteroids, but his condition deteriorated. He ultimately succumbed to septic shock in the setting of febrile neutropenia.

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